

Trade-off among different metrics (models are trained targeting absld)

(a) SJF

(b) F1

These figures show the scheduling performance of SchedInspector (models trained to target absld) and corresponding base schedulers on four different job traces and three performance metrics. Y-axis are average bsld (absld), utilization, and maximal bsld (mbsld), respectively. For absld and mbsld, smaller values are better; For utilization, larger values are better. These results show SchedInspector performs well towards mbsld and trade-off with lower system utilization.